

Results

Table 3. The physical properties and chemical formula of the new oseltamivir derivatives.

Compound	M.P. °C	Yield%	Physical appearance	Molecular formula
Os-Phe	180-183	70	White	C ₂₃ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₅
Os-Ile	206-208	67	Yellowish	C ₁₉ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₅
Os-Ser	145-147	73	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₆
Os-Tyr	210-212	61	Dark yellow	C ₂₃ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₆
Os-Phe-Hydroxamate	175-177	68	Brown	C ₂₃ H ₃₅ N ₅ O ₅
Os-Ile-Hydroxamate	215-217	63	Light brown	C ₁₉ H ₃₅ N ₅ O ₅
Os-Ser-Hydroxamate	168-170	67	Dark brown	C ₁₇ H ₃₁ N ₅ O ₆
Os-Tyr-Hydroxamate	222-224	65	Dark yellow	C ₂₃ H ₃₅ N ₅ O ₆
Oseltamivir acid	170-176	---	White	C ₁₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄

Table 4. The spectral analysis of the new Oseltamivir carboxamides and their hybrid molecules with hydroxamate.

Compound	FT-IR spectra	¹ H-NMR spectra	¹³ C-NMR spectra
Os-Phe	3338 – 2787, OH str. vib.; 3367 and 3312 NH str. vib.; 3233, 3213, NH ₂ str. vib.; 1716 C=O str. vib. of COOH; 1655 and 1639 amide C=O str. vib.	0.85 (t, 6H), 1.38 (q, 4H), 1.58 (s, 2H, NH ₂), 1.95 (s, 3H), 2.04 (d, 2H), 2.37 (d, 2H), 2.66 (t, 1H), 2.85 (q, 1H), 3.11 (m, 1H), 3.32 (t, 1H), 4.27 (t, 1H), 6.05-6.63 (dd, 1H), 7.27-6.69 (m, 5H, Ar.), 8.38 (s, 1H, NH), 8.47 (s, 1H, NH), 12.49 (s, 1H, OH)	9.84, 23.79, 28.66, 36.67, 49.14, 52.69, 55.06, 61.12, 74.43, 81.61, 127.12-129.96 (Ar.), 136.94, 138.93, 165.58 (C=O), 171.19 (C=O), 171.52 (C=O)
Os-Ile	3389 – 2556 OH str. vib., 3345 and 3333 NH str., 3246 and 3219 NH ₂ str. vib., 1716 C=O of COOH, 1655 and 1618 amide C=O str.	0.83 (t, 6H), 0.98 (d, 6H), 1.19 (q, 4H), 1.35 (m, 1H), 1.85 (s, 2H, NH ₂), 2.00 (s, 3H), 2.20 (d, 2H), 2.35 (t, 1H), 2.85 (t, 1H), 3.65 (m, 1H), 4.12 (t, 1H), 4.39 (d, 1H), 6.59-6.68 (dd, 1H), 8.35 (s, 1H, NH), 8.41 (t, 1H, NH), 12.39 (s, 1H, OH)	10.00, 14.52, 18.74, 23.56, 26.45, 25.51, 49.20, 52.64, 61.11, 74.36, 81.58, 127.42, 138.91, 165.56 C=O, 170.55 C=O, 171.15 C=O
Os-Ser	3368 – 2500 OH str., 3376 and 3319 NH str., 3222 and 3200 NH ₂ str. vib., 1715 C=O of COOH, 1698 and 1613 amide C=O str. vib.	0.74 (t, 6H), 1.20 (q, 4H), 1.38 (s, 2H, NH ₂), 1.86 (s, 3H), 2.40 (d, 2H), 3.02 (t, 1H), 3.403 (t, 1H), 3.58 (m, 1H), 3.62 (t, 1H), 3.73 (t, 1H), 3.90 (d, 2H), 4.13 (s, 1H, OH), 6.66-6.85 (dd, 1H), 8.22 (s, 1H, NH), 8.36 (s, 1H, NH), 11.89 (s, 1H, OH).	10.00, 15.04, 23.55, 25.50, 45.48, 49.36, 54.93, 59.91, 74.53, 81.59, 127.40, 138.88, 165.54 C=O, 170.52 C=O, 171.21 C=O

Os-Tyr	3368 – 2500 OH str. vib., 3376 and 3319 NH str., 3222 and 3200 NH ₂ str. vib., 1715 C=O of COOH, 1698 and 1653 amide C=O str. vib.	0.74 (t, 6H), 1.18 (q, 4H), 1.35 (s, 2H, NH ₂), 1.86 (s, 3H), 2.34 (d, 2H), 2.85 (d, 2H), 3.28 (t, 1H), 3.26 (q, 1H), 3.74 (m, 1H), 4.12 (t, 1H), 4.28 (t, 1H), 6.59 -6.63 (dd, 1H), 6.69- 7.04 (m, 4H, Ar.), 8.31 (s, 1H, NH), 8.33 (s, 1H, NH), 8.34 (s, 1H, OH), 12.85 (s, 1H, OH). 12.85 (s, 1H, OH)	9.83, 23.79, 26.07, 28.62, 49.19, 49.35 52.66, 61.13, 74.39 81.57, 115.76 (Ar.), 128.22 (Ar.), 130.89 (Ar.), 138.91 (Ar.), 127.43,138.21, 165.57, 167.33 171.17
Os-Phe- Hydroxamate	3350 and 3320 NH str., 3285 OH str. vib., 3212 and 3205 NH ₂ str., 1712 oxime C=O str. vib., 1652 and 1630 amide C=O str. vib.	0.75 (t, 6H), 1.13 (q, 4H), 1.42 (s, 2H, NH ₂), 1.84s, 3H), 1.87 (d, 2H), 2.97 (d, 2H), 3.01 (t, 1H), 3.42 (q, 1H), 3.7 (m, 1H), 3.78 (t, 1H), 4.11 (t, 1H), 6.63 (dd, 1H), 7.25 (m, 5H, Ar.), 7.95 (s, 1H, NH), 8.11 (s, 1H, NH), 8.22 (s, 1H, NH), 11.21 (s, 1H, OH).	9.46, 23.62, 26.08, 29.53, 46.16, 49.71, 53.91, 60.57, 72.21 81.59, 126.86-149.47 (Ar.), 129.71, 138.62, 165.71 (C=O), 171.1 (C=O), 171.55 (C=O).
Os-Ile- Hydroxamate	NH str., 3286, oxime OH str. vib., 3210 and 3190 asym. and sym. NH ₂ str. vib., 1712 oxime C=O, 1641 and 1733 amide C=O str. vib.	0.75 (t, 6H), 0.89 (d, 6H), 1.19 (q, 4H), 1.38 (m, 1H), 1.83 (s, 2H, NH ₂), 1.87 (s, 3H), 2.96 (d, 2H), 3.00 (t, 1H), 3.27 (t, 1H), 3.68 (m, 1H), 3.93 (t, 1H), 4.12 (d, 1H), 6.67- 6.70 (dd, 1H), 7.93 (s, 1H, NH), 8.00 (s, 1H, NH), 8.25 (s, 1H, NH), 10.47 (s, 1H, OH).	10.12, 15.34, 18.75, 23.47, 23.58, 25.55, 49.94, 54.76, 61.01, 74.79, 81.60, 128.77, 138.59, 165.81 (C=O), 170.34 (C=O), 171.19 (C=O).
Os-Ser- Hydroxamate	3390 and 3301 NH str. vib., 3265 OH str. vib., 3215 and 3195 asym. and sym. NH ₂ str., 1714 oxime C=O str. vib., 1655 and 1638 amide C=O str. vib.	0.83 (t, 6H), 1.17 (q, 4H), 1.32 (s, 2H), 1.85 (s, 3H), 2.38 (d, 2H), 3.18 (t, 1H), 3.31 (t, 1H), 3.75 (m, 1H), 3.87 (t, 1H), 4.10 (t, 1H), 4.27 (d, 2H), 4.39 (s, 1H), 6.58- 6.67 (dd, 1H), 7.90 (s, 1H), 8.01 (s, 1H), 8.37 (s, 1H), 10.62 (s, 1H).	8.92, 14.52, 23.76, 25.53, 45.80, 49.42, 56.63, 60.53, 74.45, 81.64, 127.47, 138.7, 165.58 (C=O), 170.55 (C=O), 171.33 (C=O)
Os-Tyr- Hydroxamate	3370 and 3310 amide NH str. vib.; 3270 oxime OH str. vib.; 3201 and 3185 asym. and sym. NH ₂ str. vib., 1710 C=O str. vib., 1643 and 1625 amide C=O str. vib.	0.83 (t, 6H), 1.19 (q, 4H), 1.39 (s, 2H, NH ₂), 1.86 (s, 3H), 2.23 (d, 2H), 2.82 (d, 2H), 3.14 (t, 1H), 3.54 (q, 1H), 3.78 (m, 1H), 4.12 (t, 1H), 4.14 (t, 1H), 6.46 -6.68 (dd, 1H), 7.02- 7.04 (m, 4H, Ar.), 7.99 (s, 1H, NH), 8.05 (s, 1H, NH), 8.29 (s, 1H, OH), 10.62 (s, 1H, OH).	9.35, 23.59, 26.08, 29.66, 47.33, 49.74, 54.40, 61.03, 74.75, 81.56 115.77, 138.42, 138.65, 139.67, 156.44 (Ar.), 165.76 (C=O), 167.05(C=O) 171.07 (C=O).